

New paper about data publishing in DSI

Portal Admin

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[SCIENCE NEWS]

This post is to inform you about the publishing of an online-first version of our article titled “Critical remarks on current practices of data article publishing: issues, challenges, and recommendations”. The manuscript has gone through approximately 18 months of preparation and peer review to appear in the journal *Data Science and Informetrics* (DSI), finally.

Among various works, this publication deserves a few lines of introduction because it stands out from the remaining for understandable reasons. First, although this portal spends a substantial portion of its content dealing with data and information processing, the paper is perhaps the only one dedicated to data publishing and the emerging philosophy behind that. Second, following our own process of contributing to and reusing published data sets in peer-reviewed journals, what we have learned will likely add value to the widely adopted views concerning the FAIR Principles [2].

Illustration: DSI cover design (<https://dsi.hdu.edu.cn/pro.aspx?ClassID=45>)

The analysis and view presented in the paper [1] have also enabled us to conceive the recent definition of value based on the concept of information entropy and interactions [3].

DSI is the official journal of the China Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics, sponsored by Hangzhou Dianzi University and Tsinghua University.

References

- [1] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH. (2024). Critical remarks on current practices of data article publishing: issues, challenges, and recommendations. *Data Science and Informetrics*, 4(2), 1-14. <https://dsi.hdu.edu.cn/NewsDetail.aspx?ID=229>
- [2] Wilkinson MD, *et al.* (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOARN>

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